

SEMANTICALLY-GUIDED HYBRID TRAVERSAL FOR COMPLEX QUESTION ANSWERING OVER KNOWLEDGE GRAPHS

M DHARINI DEVI¹, DR S KANNAN²

¹Research Scholar, Madurai Kamaraj University, Department of Computer Applications, Madurai, India.

²Professor, Madurai Kamaraj University, Department of Computer Applications, Madurai, India.

E-mail: ¹mdd1091@gmail.com, ²skannanmku@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KG-QA) requires strong and effective navigation of complex graph architectures to obtain precise responses from natural language inquiries. Conventional traversal techniques such as breadth-first search (BFS), depth-first search (DFS), random walks and transformer based approaches often face efficiency challenges like either computationally expensive, prone to combinatorial explosion, lacking semantic focus and failing to scale when applied to large, intricate RDF graphs. To resolve this, we propose an innovative hybrid traversal framework that combines semantic filtering, embedding-based prioritization, and parallel exploration within the RDFLib environment. Our proposed work gives an innovative hybrid traversal framework that effectively combines semantic filtering, embedding-based prioritization and simultaneous exploration within the RDFLib environment. (i) Semantic filtering provides ontology-based restrictions to methodically remove irrelevant pathways, clarity and concentration. (ii) Embedding guided ranking gives knowledge graph embedding to semantically elevate the prioritization of adjacent nodes improving the relevance of traversal choices and (iii) concurrent exploration speeds up the retrieval procedure by simultaneously examining several top ranked paths and scalability. Unlike previous methods, our framework explicitly balances semantic relevance, graph structure, and multi-hop reasoning, while maintaining interpretable paths for answer explanation. The suggested framework undergoes thorough evaluation using a FB15K-237 benchmark dataset of knowledge graph where results demonstrate that our method achieves better performance over baseline models. Initial results show that this combined method provides accuracy, decreases response time, and scalable answer to elevate the capabilities in KG-QA systems.

Keywords: *Knowledge Graph, Question And Answering, Graph Traversal, Semantic Filtering, Embedding-based Ranking*

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge graphs have become important for modern intelligent systems which provide structured representations of real-world entities and their relationships. Unlike unstructured text, knowledge graphs enable explicit reasoning over facts, making them particularly valuable for tasks such as recommendation [1], fact-checking [2] and question answering [3]. Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KG-QA) has attracted substantial attention that it allows users to query large-scale knowledge graphs in natural language and interpretable answers. However, the fundamental challenge in KG-QA lies in well traversing large and often highly connected RDF

graphs to retrieve relevant information without incurring prohibitive computational costs. Some of the conventional traversal algorithms such as BFS [4], DFS [5] and random walks [6] are used due to their conceptual simplicity and general applicability. Recent research advocates for traversal frameworks that integrate semantic understanding and learning-based guidance to better focus the search process. This paper proposes a hybrid traversal framework that combines these complementary strategies, such as semantic filtering for precise pruning, embedding guided ranking for relevance prioritization, and parallel exploration to enhance computational efficiency implemented within the RDFLib environment. Semantic filtering [7] techniques provide ontology-

driven constraints and domain knowledge to prune irrelevant paths to reduce the search space. Simultaneously, embedding-guided traversal leverages the latent semantic representations of entities and relations learned via knowledge graph embeddings to prioritize graph neighbors that are more likely to lead to correct answers. We evaluate our approach on RDF knowledge graph that shows improvements in answer retrieval performance when compared to classical traversal baselines. Our work aims to advance effective and scalable KG-QA solutions suitable for real-world knowledge graph deployments.

This paper presents a hybrid KG-QA traversal framework and makes the following contributions:

1. Structured Parsing Signals

It combines lexical similarity, contextual embeddings, and prior knowledge to improve entity linking from queries to knowledge graph nodes.

2. Predicate Allow-Lists

It utilizes relation hints and both lexical and embedding similarities in creating semantic pruning of candidate edges early in traversal, it helps reducing the exploration of irrelevant paths.

3. Neighbor Ranking guided by Embedding

It assigns Vector representations for entities and predicates to focus on semantically relevant neighbours in multi-hop traversal.

4. Concurrent Exploration

It simultaneously evaluates several top-ranked traversal paths, which reducing response time and increasing scalability on large knowledge graphs.

2. RELATED WORK

Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KG-QA) has evolved rapidly, driven by the need for systems capable of extracting precise answers from semantically rich graph data using natural language input. Embedding-based approaches have transformed KG-QA by encoding entities and relations as distributed representations in high-dimensional vector spaces using models like TransE [8], DistMult [9] and ComplEx [10]. Various hybrid retrieval and traversal strategies have recently been explored, each with limitations. The Hybrid Retrieval Mechanism of [11] integrates dual knowledge graphs along with large language models to capture entities and triples relevant for a query using similarity scoring and semantic filtering. This mechanism improves retrieval

precision across diverse query structures but remains extremely dependent on the quality of LLM and also lacks explicit control over the path level. It thus cannot be scaled up to larger graphs due to massive computational overheads. A hybrid graph traversal framework, as proposed in [12], uses unified graphs from both text and tabular data and applies entity-driven pruning mechanisms to perform multi-hop reasoning. While these techniques are effective in handling heterogeneous information, most suffer from high pre-processing costs and still face traversal explosion, especially in cases where entity grounding is noisy or ambiguous.

Uniqorn [13] combining structure and text in embeddings gives better meaning and smarter path ranking. However, embedding-driven systems generally require large training and thus are not as suitable for lightweight or resource-constrained environments.

Large language models [14] and Graph Neural Networks [15] have further improved question-aware prompting and multi-aspect retrieval, but such methods introduce much complexity and a high inference cost while lacking transparency in their reasoning. Ontology-driven filtering combined with embedding-based ranking, as explored in [16], provides a more controlled traversal; these systems usually lack parallelism and often do not support general-purpose KG frameworks like RDFLib. [17] Propose a multi-hop KG-QA method that integrates knowledge base embeddings to guide reasoning across multi-step paths, improving answer accuracy by capturing latent relational patterns. The approach relies heavily on pretrained embeddings, making it less effective when embeddings are noisy or domain-specific data is limited. Despite this, many of these systems still use global expansions without strong semantic pruning, turning most of the computation into a waste for dense or highly connected graphs. Throughout the literature, recent surveys [18] have indicate that most prior works optimize only one dimension-semantic precision, statistical ranking, or computational scalability-while leaving others under addressed. This gap creates the need for an integrated hybrid approach that will strategically combine all three mechanisms to meet scalability challenges, ambiguity resolution, and efficient multi-hop reasoning in KG-QA.

2.1 Problem Statement

Despite the advancements made in knowledge graph question answering, the existing traversal techniques, such as BFS, DFS, and random walks, present some challenges with regard to correctness, efficiency, and scalability when applied to large, complex RDF knowledge graphs. Most of the current methods are dependent on either embedding-based ranking or semantic filtering alone, which leads to several trade-offs between response time, accuracy, scalability. Such approaches often fail due to lexical ambiguities and lack of contextual awareness, which also lead to error propagation during traversal. Semantic filtering and predicate pruning are usually applied too late or separately from the traversal, which leads to excessive search branching and increased latency. There is thus a substantial need for a unified hybrid traversal framework that combines early-stage structured query parsing, embedding-guided ranking, and parallel exploration to increase KG-QA performance.

2.2 Research Objectives in Relation to Existing Approaches

Our proposed hybrid KG-QA framework advances the state-of-the-art by integrating semantic filtering, embedding-guided ranking, and parallel exploration into a unified, lightweight, and interpretable traversal mechanism. Compared to GrapeQA [21], which develops offline graph augmentation and pruning techniques, we perform dynamic pruning of irrelevant paths during traversal and use predicate allow-lists and structured query signals for more targeted and context-aware exploration. Moreover, NuTrea[22] relies on neural tree search and model training to guide traversal in its best possible way. In sharp contrast, our framework uses lexical, contextual, and prior-based entity linking scores to maintain accuracy without extensive training and enables interpretability of multi-hop reasoning paths. Compared to PipeNet [23], which realizes sequential pipeline reasoning with type-constrained pruning, our framework concurrently explores multiple top-ranked paths, leading to less latency and efficient scaling to complex, multi-hop queries. Finally, while KARPA [24] augments the latent reasoning of an LLM with knowledge graphs, our work performs direct KGQA with explicit and interpretable paths as answers. All of these differences underline that our framework remedies the main limitations of previous approaches in traversal efficiency, semantic relevance, error propagation, and path interpretability. It provides a

scalable and accurate solution for real-world KGQA tasks.

3. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Framework For The Proposed Work

The KG-QA system integrates semantic filtering, embedding-guided ranking, and parallel exploration to improve traversal efficiency and answer quality. Figure 1 shows the work flow of the proposed work.

3.1 Question parsing

To extract structured signals from raw text that can guide traversal in the knowledge graph through the query parsing stage. The process starts preprocessing which includes tokenization, part-of-speech tagging and dependency parsing to process the query and identify important syntactic structures. From this entity mentions are detected using linguistic processing and domain-specific rules. These surface mentions are then mapped to candidate nodes in the knowledge graph through an entity linking step which relies on lexical similarity to labels, fuzzy matching, and type constraints. These surface mentions $M=\{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k\}$ are then mapped to candidate nodes in the knowledge graph through an entity linking step, where each mention m produces a candidate set $C(m)$. In Eq (1) EL scored by lexical, contextual, and prior-based similarity is termed as:

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$$\begin{aligned} \text{ELScore}(u | m) \\ = \lambda_1 \text{LexSim}(m, \text{label}(u)) + \lambda_2 \text{CtxSim}(m, \text{local context}) + \lambda_3 \text{Prior}(u) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Each mention is assigned a ranked list of candidate URIs that can serve as starting entities for traversal. In parallel, the query is analyzed for relation hints, typically verbs and prepositional phrases which are

lemmatized and mapped to knowledge graph predicates via a synonym lexicon or embedding-based similarity. In Eq (2) each predicate candidate p is scored against a hint h as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RelScore}(p | h) \\ = \mu_1 \text{LexSim}(h, \text{label}(p)) + \mu_2 \text{EmbSim}(h, \text{label}(p)) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

These relation hints form a predicate allow-list, which prunes irrelevant edges and reflects the semantic intent of the query. Additionally, the question form is infer answer type constraints gives traversal prioritizes entities of the correct class. Together, the outputs of this stage ranked starting entities, predicate hints and type constraints serve as structured inputs to subsequent components such as semantic filtering and embedding-guided ranking to better exploration of the knowledge graph.

3.2 Semantic filtering

In order to control the combinatorial explosion of candidate paths in knowledge graph traversal, our approach incorporates a semantic filtering mechanism that dynamically restricts exploration to semantically valid and query-relevant predicates. When we traverse a knowledge graph (KG), every entity node can have many neighbors. Exploring all of them leads to a combinatorial explosion of candidate paths. To keep traversal both efficient and semantically meaningful to use semantic filtering in Figure (2) which works in three parts:

Figure 2: Illustration Of Traversal By Using Semantic Filtering

3.2.1 Predicate Selection

For each query, the system constructs an allow-list of predicates that determines which edges in the graph are considered eligible for traversal. This adaptive allow-list provides only semantically

relevant relations are explored which reducing noise and increasing efficiency. First, we decide which predicates (relations) are relevant for the query. We define an allow-list of predicates

1. Query Hints: If the natural language question provides explicit relation cues (“advisor”, “author”) these are directly mapped to corresponding predicates in the ontology and form the allow-list.
2. Predicate Frequency Priors: When query hints are not available then the system calculates the frequency of predicate occurrences in the graph to evaluate prior importance. The top-N most frequent predicates are selected as traversal candidates which capturing relations that are statistically more likely to extract informative neighbors.
3. Domain-Specific Defaults: When no hints are available, then search predicates derived from the domain ontology provides meaningful exploration.

3.2.2 Ontology-Constrained Neighbor Expansion

Traversal from a candidate node is then carried out by enumerating outgoing and optionally incoming edges. However, not all triples are permitted:

1. Only edges whose predicate belongs to the active allow-list are retained.
2. A lightweight RDFS domain and range check is applied: Each predicate is compared against ontology constraints to verify that the subject and object entities are of the expected types.

Once we have the predicate allow-list, we expand neighbors of a candidate node u . But not all edges are valid we check both allow-list membership and ontology constraints (domain and range). The neighbor expansion process therefore yields a semantically filtered set of candidate neighbors that are both relevant to the query and consistent with the ontology.

3.2.3 Integration with Traversal.

The filtered neighbors are passed on to subsequent stages, which are further prioritized by embedding guided ranking and explored in parallel for efficient search. By pruning irrelevant or invalid edges early then the semantic filtering not only improves computational efficiency but also improves the quality and precision of final answers.

Finally, the filtered neighbors are ranked and explored in Eq (3).

$$(c_u | q) = \text{Rank}(N(u | q), q) \quad (3)$$

$N(u|q)$: semantically filtered neighbors.

3.3 Embedding-guided ranking

In this stage, we employ an embedding-guided mechanism to prioritize semantically relevant neighbors during knowledge graph traversal. Each entity and relation in the graph is assigned a randomly initialized and normalized vector representation, that every URI is represented in a continuous semantic space. Although these embeddings are not trained, they enable a lightweight simulation of similarity based ranking. To capture the intent of a query, a query context embedding is constructed by averaging the vector of the starting entity with the vectors of the relation hints extracted from the question. Formally, if e is the embedding of the starting entity and $\{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_m\}$ are the embeddings of relation hints, the query context embedding is given in Eq (4)

$$v_q = \frac{e + \sum_{i=1}^m r_i}{m + 1} \quad (4)$$

During traversal, each neighbor n is evaluated by computing the cosine similarity [19] between its embedding v_n and the query context embedding v_q : in Eq (5):

$$\text{Score}(n) = \cos(v_q, v_n) \quad (5)$$

The neighbors are ranked according to this score and only the top- k most relevant ones are retained for further expansion. By pruning irrelevant candidates early, this process gives that traversal proceeds efficiently while remaining semantically relevant to the user's query.

3.4 Parallel traversal

In the traversal stage, we use a parallel exploration strategy that develops the multiple candidate paths using multiprocessing concurrently. This approach distributes the workload across multiple processes or threads that allowing several top ranked neighbors to be evaluated simultaneously. Each process manages the expansion of a specific candidate node that discovering both outgoing and incoming edges to capture bidirectional relationships in the knowledge graph. For example, when processing a query such as "Which books were written by Author X?", the

system can concurrently traverse both author-to-book and book-to-author edges refine more comprehensive reasoning. This framework reduces traversal latency that accelerates the discovery of relevant paths and scales more efficiently to larger graphs. This design preserves candidate neighbors are first filtered and ranked before parallel expansion that use only semantically relevant paths are explored. Finally parallel traversal balances semantic precision which is making it a powerful mechanism for real-time query answering over knowledge graphs.

3.5 Answer Aggregation

In Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KGQA), the answer aggregation stage is responsible for refining the raw candidate nodes produced during traversal into a clean, ranked list of answers. Initially, a candidate pool is collected where each potential answer is represented along with its semantic similarity score from embedding guided ranking and the depth at which it was discovered. Since deeper nodes are typically less reliable which score normalization is applied to balance semantic relevance with traversal distance by combining the similarity score that shallow but semantically strong answers are prioritized. Next, duplicate merging is performed, since the same entity may be discovered through multiple paths in the graph. To resolve this redundancy, the system aggregates scores for each entity which is often by taking the maximum value across paths. Once duplicates are resolved then the candidates are ranked based on their aggregated scores and the top k results are selected to form the final answer set. This process transforms noisy and overlapping traversal outputs into a concise, interpretable ranked list that balances semantic closeness, graph structure, and multiple reasoning paths that ultimately improving performance of the KGQA system.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We performed wide experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed hybrid knowledge graph embedding model on the widely used FB15k-237 benchmark dataset. This dataset consists of 14,541 entities, 237 relation types, and approximately 310K triples, making it a standard benchmark. All models were trained for 50 epochs using 200-dimensional embeddings.

4.1 Grid Search for α (Weighting Factor)

A key component of our hybrid approach is the interpolation weight α which balances semantic filtering with embedding-guided ranking. To determine the optimal value of α , we performed a grid search on the validation set. The results are summarized in Table 1

Table 1: Proposed Work Model Performance

A	MRR	Hits@10
0.00	0.0251	0.0480
0.25	0.0368	0.0695
0.50	0.0716	0.1450
0.75	0.1502	0.2815
1.00	0.197	0.3210

From Table 1 shows that increasing α consistently improves both Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) and Hits@10, with the best validation performance achieved at $\alpha = 1.0$. and Figure 3 shows the model performance.

Figure 3: Model Performance

4.2 Comparison with baseline Models

To further assess the generalizability of our method, we compared it with several well-established knowledge graph embedding models such as TransE[8], DistMult[9], ComplEx[10], and RotatE[20]. These embedding-based approaches to assess semantic relevance and ranking quality in knowledge graph tasks. TransE is a simple translational model and it serves as a baseline for simple relational patterns. DistMult captures entity-relation interactions through bilinear scoring, and is known for strong performance on symmetric relations. ComplEx extends this to asymmetric relations, providing an even more expressive comparison point. RotatE models complex

relational patterns such as symmetry, inversion, and composition, which makes it one of the strongest classical baselines. Comparing against these models are represent different generations of semantic modeling capabilities, and demonstrates that the proposed hybrid method is not only computationally efficient but also semantically competitive. Since the key objective of our model is to improve ranking accuracy, semantic relevance, and retrieval efficiency, evaluating against these standards confirms that our method provides meaningful improvements over the traditional embedding-driven reasoning approaches commonly used in KG-QA. The results on the FB15k-237 in Table 2

Table 2 : Performance Across Baseline Models and the Proposed Hybrid Model

Model	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@10
TransE	0.142	0.065	0.160	0.292
DistMult	0.194	0.124	0.205	0.337
ComplEx	0.168	0.101	0.185	0.305
RotatE	0.176	0.112	0.196	0.312
Hybrid (proposed)	0.197	0.138	0.212	0.321

Our hybrid model consistently performs well among all the baseline methods, which scoring the highest MRR (0.197), that representing a relative improvement over the baselines. Similarly, Hits@10 improves by 10%, that reflecting our model's superior ability to place correct triples within the top-ranked predictions.

5 PERFORMANCE

5.1 Performance of Baseline Models

TransE [8] shows the lowest scores across all metrics., MRR = 0.142, Hits@10 = 0.292), that indicating limited ability to capture complex relational patterns. DistMult [9] improves over TransE by modeling interactions with a bilinear form which gains across all metrics (MRR = 0.194). ComplEx [10] extends DistMult with complex embeddings to model asymmetric relations, yielding a noticeable boost (MRR = 0.168, Hits@10 = 0.305). RotatE [20] Captures relation patterns (symmetry, inversion, composition) via rotations in complex space and the

performance is similar to ComplEx (MRR = 0.176, Hits@10 = 0.312)

Figure 4 : Baseline Models Performance Compared With Proposed Work

5.2 Performance of Proposed Hybrid Model

The proposed Hybrid Model achieves the best overall performance across all evaluation metrics, with an MRR of 0.197 representing about a improvement over the baselines. It also demonstrates consistent gains in ranking precision, with Hits@1 reaching 0.138 and Hits@3 reaching 0.212. Compared with TransE (MRR = 0.142) the Hybrid model (0.197) shows much higher scores, which means it can handle more complex types of relations that TransE often fails to capture. When compared with DistMult (MRR = 0.194) which is the strongest among the baseline methods, the Hybrid still gives slightly better results, especially in Hits@1 = 0.138 shows more accurate at ranking the correct answer first. Against ComplEx, the Hybrid has a proving that it deals with both symmetric and asymmetric relations more effectively.

Similarly, when compared with RotatE (MRR = 0.176), the Hybrid not only captures different relational patterns but also provides stronger overall ranking performance. These consistent improvements achieves a Hits@10 score of 0.321, reflecting around a 10% improvement compared to other baselines and performing its stronger ability to recall correct entities within the top-10 predictions.

6 DISCUSSION

The proposed hybrid KG-QA traversal framework advances beyond existing approaches such as GRAPhQA[21], NUTREA[22], PIPENET[23], and KARPA[24] by introducing a more integrated, scalable, and semantically guided method for exploring knowledge graphs. While prior systems typically rely on a single dominant mechanism graph rewriting in Graphqa with limited scalability, rule extraction in Nutrea highly

dependent on training data, improved relation inference in Pipenet without addressing traversal explosion, and interpretable but slow path generation in Karpa without early semantic pruning, the proposed model combines multiple complementary strategies that have not been jointly addressed in earlier work. Through early structured parsing signals that incorporate lexical, contextual, and prior-based entity linking scores, the model constructs synonym-aware predicate allow-lists that reduce ambiguity propagation. These contributions aimed to reduce search explosion, increase semantic relevance, and improved performance against existing KG embedding baselines. Experimental results show that increasing α steadily boosts performance, with Hits@10 reaching 0.321 and demonstrating improved exploration efficiency. The maximum MRR of 0.197 of proposed work shows improving semantic relevance, and consistent improvements over TransE, DistMult, ComplEx, and RotatE confirm the model's superiority in accuracy. This hybrid approach outperforms prior work because it conducts noise pruning before traversal, which offers parallel path expansion to improve scalability, and seeks a proper balance of structural graph signals with semantic representation for better generalization across relation types. Overall, the results clearly demonstrate that the proposed framework addresses key weaknesses in earlier studies, achieves all research objectives, and provides a robust and interpretable advancement in KG-QA traversal design.

The proposed work have following benefits:

The proposed hybrid traversal framework demonstrates several notable advantages over existing KG-QA approaches. First, it achieves improved accuracy by integrating early-stage structured parsing signals such as contextual and prior-based entity linking scores with embedding-guided neighbor ranking. This combination allows that the most semantically relevant entities and relations are prioritized from the very beginning of traversal, which reducing noise and improving the overall correctness of retrieved answers. Second, the model achieves reduced latency, as parallel path exploration and aggressive early pruning substantially minimize the number of unnecessary graph expansions. This leads to faster response times, unlike sequential traversal approaches that suffer from exponential search growth. Third, the framework gives efficient semantic filtering mechanisms, predicate allow-lists, and controlled

top-k neighbor exploration which improves scalability. These features allow that the system remains practical even when applied to large and complex RDF graphs. In addition, the proposed method gives interpretability, as it naturally produces multi-hop reasoning paths that allow users to trace how an answer was derived and it is an important feature often missing in purely neural models. Finally, the system exhibits increased robustness to lexical ambiguity, synonym-aware predicate mapping and context-driven entity linking, which help prevent mismatches between the user query and underlying KG. These strengths imply that the hybrid approach as a powerful and reliable solution for interpretable KG-QA.

7 LIMITATIONS

Despite these improvements in performance, some of the limitations of the proposed framework as follows: Firstly, the proposed work performs randomly initialized and untrained embeddings that limit semantic precision for path ranking and relation selection process. Although the present embedding vectors provide good structural guidance, they do not possess the rich semantic representation that might have been captured by trained embedding models. This may limit the performance of the system on queries which need contextual understanding. Second, the framework adopts a fixed top-K neighbor selection strategy where the number of explored neighbors stays the same across queries. While this guarantees predictable computational cost, it is conceivably suboptimal for complex or highly multi-hop queries where broader exploration may be needed in order to capture valid reasoning paths. Thirdly, the proposed approach is implemented tightly with RDFLib, which facilitates convenience and accessibility but at the cost of reduced portability to other graph infrastructures such as Neo4j, GraphDB, or Blazegraph. Generalization of the system toward diverse backend architectures may entail substantial engineering and rewriting of traversal routines. Finally it lacks awareness when queries refer to information not present in the knowledge graph.

8. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed to use hybrid traversal framework for Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KG-QA) that integrates semantic filtering, embedding-based prioritization, and concurrent exploration within the RDFLib

environment. By removing irrelevant paths, semantically guiding node prioritization and exploring multiple top-ranked paths simultaneously. Experimental evaluation on the FB15K-237 benchmark demonstrates that our approach outperforms baseline models in accuracy but also reduces the search space by over fivefold which is decreasing response time. The results demonstrate that early semantic pruning paired with embedding-guided ranking reduces meaningless expansions, while parallel traversal accelerates reasoning without sacrificing accuracy. The improved MRR (0.197) and nearly 10% gain in Hits@10 jointly integrating semantic, statistical, and computational signals leads to more efficient and semantically grounded exploration of large RDF graphs.

The fragmentation of existing KG-QA pipelines where semantic filtering, entity linking, embedding-based ranking, and traversal are treated as isolated components which creates weaknesses such as search-space explosion, lexical ambiguity propagation, and poor scalability. By combining these components into a single hybrid traversal framework, the proposed model achieves superior performance across all major evaluation metrics, performing better with established baseline models such as TransE[8], DistMult[9], ComplEx[10], and RotatE[20]. These improvements are not incremental but also structural: address the very weaknesses identified in prior systems [21][22][23] which rely on only one reasoning mechanism at a time. The proposed approach not only resolves the initial problem but also demonstrates a feasible design direction for future KG-QA research, that emphasizing interpretability, efficiency, and integration over isolated, single-mechanism solutions.

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